

Physico-chemical Studies in the Chelate Formation of Ferric Ions with β -Resorcylic Acid

M. L. N. Reddy and U. V. Seshaiiah

The formation of a purple-red, water-soluble chelate between ferric ions and β -resorcylic acid with maximum absorption at 520 m μ has been observed. The colour is stable for several days and attains maximum intensity in the pH range of 2.8 to 3.1. The composition of the chelate (1:1) has been evaluated by Job's and molar-ratio methods, employing optical density and conductance data. The values of the dissociation constant and the free energy of formation are 0.91×10^{-4} and -5.505 kcal./mole at 25° respectively. Based on the experimental evidence, a probable constitution for the complex has been assigned.

Das-Gupta¹ suggested that β -resorcylic acid might be used as a colorimetric reagent for the detection of titanium and uranium. Mukerji and Sant² showed that β -resorcylic acid formed a 1:1 complex with mercuric ions. Tarabe and Hata³ studied the colour reactions of cobalt with various aromatic hydroxycarboxylic acids and reported that β -resorcylic acid produced a light greenish yellow colour.

β -Resorcylic acid, developing a stable purple-red colour with ferric ions, was utilised by Larner and Trout⁴ for the colorimetric estimation of iron and they observed the complex exhibiting minimum transmittance in the range of 425-450 m μ . But Vivarelli⁵ found β -resorcylic acid to form with ferric ions a complex with maximum absorbance at 510 m μ for the molar ratio of ferric to ligand at 1:1. Jatkar and Matto⁶ from the colorimetric titration of β -resorcylic acid with ferric ions at 540 m μ reported the formation of 1:1 iron resorcyate complex, but their potentiometric data indicated the formation of 1:2 and 1:3 complexes in addition to the 1:1 complex.

In view of the above contradictions regarding the nature of ferric-resorcyate complex, a detailed investigation of the above complex system has been undertaken by studying the characteristics of absorption spectra, the stoichiometry as well as determination of the dissociation constant of the complex by employing spectrophotometric and electrometric methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ferric perchlorate was prepared by dissolving $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, obtained by oxidising ferrous ammonium sulphate (E. Merck) with HNO_3 (conc.), in warm perchloric acid

1. *This Journal*, 1929, 6, 763, 855.
2. *Naturwiss.*, 1959, 46, 24.
3. *Ann. Rept. Fac. Pharm. Kanazawa University*, 1956, 6, 7.
4. *Virginia J. Sci.*, 1942, 3, 13.
5. *Chim. et ind., Milan*, 1956, 38, 461.
6. *This Journal*, 1953, 30, 775.

solution and it was diluted to 1 litre (pH 1.10). A standard β -resorcylic acid (Eastman Kodak) solution was prepared by direct weighing. Ferric alum solution ($N/10$) was prepared from an E. Merck pro-analysis sample and standardised as usual.

Absorption Spectra.—The absorption spectra, of mixtures of equimolar solutions of ferric perchlorate and β -resorcylic acid in the ratios of 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4 were measured by a Uvispek spectrophotometer. Optical density measurements show that the maximum absorption of the complex lies in the region of 520-530 $m\mu$ in all the mixtures. This evidently suggests that only one complex is formed in solution?. For further study, the optical density measurements were made at or near 520 $m\mu$.

Effect of pH.—The absorption spectra of ferric-resorcylic complex were taken at various pH values between 1.5 and 6.0, pH adjustments being made by using $N/10$ -NaOH or perchloric acid solution. The complex exhibited maximum absorption between pH 2.8 and 3.1 (Fig. 1, curve B). Measurements of pH were made with a Ludwig pH-meter, type-12.

FIG. 1

- A: Beer's law plots at 520 $m\mu$ and pH 2.9. x = ml of 0.001 M metal ion added to 10 ml of 0.01 M ligand (total volume: 25 ml).
 B: Influence of pH on absorbance at 520 $m\mu$.
 C: x = ml of 0.02 M ferric ion added to 25 ml of 0.004 M ligand.

Stability of Colour of the Complex.—The colour of the complex was found to be quite stable over a period of 6 days and it faded away little after a week. The complex obeyed Beer-Lambert's law in the range 5-1000 p.p.m. of iron (Fig. 1, curve A). Incidentally β -resorcylic acid can be well used as a spectrophotometric reagent for the estimation of

ferric ions, but it suffers from the disadvantage, like salicylic or sulphosalicylic acid etc., that many cations and anions interfere in the estimation, as shown by Vivarelli⁵.

Stoichiometry of the Complex.—The composition of the complex was determined by Job's method of continued variation⁶. Optical densities were measured at wave lengths 500, 520, and 540 $m\mu$ and at pH 2.9. Since the absorption due to iron perchlorate and β -resorcylic acid solutions at the aforesaid wave lengths was negligible, the optical densities were plotted against the composition of the coloured solutions (Fig. 2, curves A and B). Both the curves show peaks when the molar ratio of the metal to the ligand is 1:1. The composition of the complex was further ascertained as 1:1 by applying Job's method to conductance measurements (Fig. 2, curve C), using 0.01 M solutions of ferric alum and β -resorcylic acid.

FIG. 2. Composition of the complex by Job's method.
 A: $c = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. B: $c = 1.33 \times 10^{-4} M$. C: $c = 6.6 \times 10^{-4} M$.
 (Total volume = 25 ml; $pH = 2.9$; $\lambda = 520 m\mu$).

A potentiometric titration was also undertaken with a view to arriving at the composition of the complex. The redox potential of the ferric ion in varying amounts of β -resorcylic acid was measured, using the system:

E.M.F. measurements were made on a Leeds and Northrup potentiometer. The results are recorded in Table I. The data indicate that the maximum in $\Delta E/\Delta V$ occurs at 1:1 mole ratio of the metal ion to the ligand, revealing the formation of a complex at the aforesaid ratio and not at any other ratio, as observed by earlier workers⁶.

TABLE I

Potentiometric titration.
0.004M-Ferric alum (50ml) with 0.04M- β -resorcylic acid.

Ligand (V).	E.	$\Delta E/\Delta V$.	Ligand (V).	E.	$\Delta E/\Delta V$.
0.0 ml	461.8 mv	..	11.0 ml	437.5 mv	1.0
1.0	461.3	0.5	12.0	436.5	1.0
2.0	459.6	1.7	13.0	435.5	1.0
3.0	457.8	1.8	14.0	435.0	0.5
4.0	455.7	2.1	15.0	434.5	0.5
5.0	448.6	7.1 (max.)	16.0	434.2	0.3
6.0	445.8	2.8	17.0	434.0	0.2
7.0	443.3	2.5	18.0	433.8	0.2
8.0	441.4	1.9	19.0	433.7	0.1
9.0	439.5	1.0	20.0	433.5	0.2
10.0	438.5	1.0			

The stoichiometry of the complex was further verified by the molar-ratio method⁹ by employing both optical density and conductance data (Fig. 3, curves B and A). The curves show clear breaks at the mole ratio of 1:1, thus establishing unequivocally that ferric ions form a 1:1 complex with β -resorcylic acid.

FIG. 3. Composition of the complex by molar ratio method.

A: x =ml of 0.01M ligand to 3 ml of 0.01M metal ion (total volume 15 ml).

B: x =ml of 0.004M ligand to 4 ml of 0.004M metal ion (total volume 25 ml; pH 2.0; λ 520m μ).

9. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.

Dissociation Constant of the Complex

The dissociation constant of the chelate was determined by the method followed by Foley and Anderson¹⁰. Pairs of solutions of ferric-resorcyate complex having the same optical densities but containing different concentrations of metal ions and the chelating agent were prepared. Since the dissociation constant is the same for members of a given pair, the value of K , the dissociation constant, may be calculated from the relation:

$$K = \frac{(a_1 - x)(b_1 - x)}{x} = \frac{(a_2 - x)(b_2 - x)}{x}$$

$$x = \frac{(a_1 b_1) - (a_2 b_2)}{(a_1 + b_1) - (a_2 + b_2)}$$

where a 's and b 's denote the initial concentrations of the metal ion and the chelating agent respectively and x represents the concentration of the complex formed. The average value of K from several determinations is 0.91×10^{-4} .

The dissociation constant of the complex may also be computed from Job's curves, as worked out by Raghavarao *et al.*¹¹ for the thorium-nitroso-R salt complex. The height PQ (Fig. 2, curve B) represents the density of the complex if there were no dissociation and PR, the actual density. So the degree of dissociation is given by

$$\alpha = \frac{PQ - PR}{PQ}$$

Hence in the reaction $MR \rightleftharpoons M + R$, the dissociation constant K of the complex is given by

$$K = \frac{(\alpha^2 C)}{(1 - \alpha)} = 0.704 \times 10^{-4}$$

Further, the free energy of formation of the chelate has been calculated with the help of the relation:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta F^\circ &= RT \ln K \\ &= RT \ln 0.91 \times 10^{-4} \\ &= -5.505 \text{ kcal./mole at } 25^\circ. \end{aligned}$$

Structure of the Complex

Preliminary experiments showed that the pH of β -resorcylic acid (25 ml of 0.004 M , pH 3.15) gradually decreased by the addition of ferric alum solution (0.02 M , pH 2.95) and became almost constant at 2.50, when one equivalent of the ferric solution (5 ml) was added (Fig. 1, curve C). This evidently indicates that there is an increase in the H^+ -ion concentration of the mixture, which is only possible by the displacement of the hydroxyl

10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 909.

11. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14B, 278.

hydrogen of the rosorcyate by the ferric ion. The chelation might take place as suggested below:

Similar structures have been assigned to ferric-salicylate¹² and manganese-*o*-cresotato complexes¹³.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
 OSMANIA UNIVERSITY,
 HYDRABAD.

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12. Kuznetsov, *J. Gen. Chem., USSR*, 1950, 20, 816.

13. Kachhawa and Bhattacharya, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 399.